

Science

THE EFFICACY OF DASHMOOLADI CHURNA IN ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Ayurveda is one of the most ancient medical sciences of the world. It describes the basic and applied aspects of life process, health, disease and its management with the sound base of principles and approaches.

21st century is a world of industrialization & fast life which has created various life style disorders. Hypertension is one of life threatening gift of today's life, which is psychosomatic, hereditary and occurring as a result of aging. It is also called as a silent or hidden killer because most of sufferers (85%) are asymptomatic and as per available reports, in more than 94% cases of hypertension under lying cause is not found. Such patients are said to have Essential Hypertension (EHT). Hypertension is one of the leading causes of the Global burden of disease.

60 Years male patient suffering from Anidra, Shirashoola, Bhrama, Daurbalya, Klama, Krodhaprachurya since last two months. He came to our hospital for Ayurvedic treatment. With our unique herbal combination of drug, his all symptoms got controlled.

This is one single study on Dashmooladi churna to evaluate the efficiency on Essential hypertension.

Keywords: Dashmooladi Churna; Essential Hypertension; Case Study.

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1. Introduction

Hypertension is one of the leading cause of the Global burden of disease. Approximately 7.6 million deaths (13-15% of total) & 92 million disability-adjusted life years worldwide were attributed to high blood pressure.¹ The prevalence rate of hypertension increases with age. The prevalence of hypertension increases to 75% to 80% in individuals above 70 years of age.² Genetic factors also contribute to prevalence of hypertension. Hypertension is common in Black Races,

worldwide. Up to the age of 60 years, male individuals are more prone to the hypertension while after 60 years of age, female individuals are more prone to hypertension. Hypertension is said to be Primary/Essential when there is no obvious precipitating factor, or the much less common secondary hypertension where there is some identifiable cause.³

Our ancient *Acharyas* of Ayurveda explained various important properties of Herbal drugs in *Samhitas & Nighantus*. With the help of those references in this topic, we are going to assess the effect of the *Dashmooladi Churna* in essential hypertension.

Case study

A 60 Years male patient came to us with chief complaints of –

- *Anidra*
- *Shirashoola*
- *Bhrama*
- *Daurbalya*
- *Klama*
- *Krodhaprachurya*

Patient had above complaints since last 2 months.

History of past illness

No H/o Dm/ Any other major surgery

History of personal illness

The patient was normal 2 months back, since than patient have been suffering from *Anidra, Shirashoola, Bhrama, Daurbalya, Klama, Krodhaprachurya*. For best Ayurvedic treatment patient came to our hospital.

2. Personal History

- 1) *Ahara* - mix (Vegetarian and Non- Vegetarian both)
- 2) *Vihara* - *Diwaswap*, sanitary life style.
- 3) *Koshtha* - *Madyam*
- 4) *Agni- Vishama*
- 5) *Nidra* - *Anidra*
- 6) *Vyasana* - Tea, Tobacco chewing.

3. Ashtavidha-Pariksha

<i>Nadi</i>	: 76/min	<i>Shabda</i>	: <i>spastha</i>
<i>Mala</i>	: <i>samyaka</i>	<i>Sparsha</i>	: <i>anushsn</i>
<i>Mutra</i>	: <i>samyaka</i>	<i>Druk</i>	: <i>prakrut</i>
<i>Jivha</i>	: <i>niram</i>	<i>Akruti</i>	: <i>krush</i>

4. General Examination

Pulse - 76/min

Blood Pressure - 158/90 mm/hg

Weight- 54 kg

Prakruti - vata pradhana pittanubandhi.

5. Material and Method

Material

<i>Dashmooladi Churna:</i>	
Contents:	
1	Dashmool-1gm
2	Shankhapushpi-500mg
3	Jatamansi-500mg
4	Punarnava-500mg
5	Vacha-250mg
6	Ela-250mg

Method

Preparation

- Required quantities of *dravyas* was taken & fine powder formed.
- *Dashmooladi Churna* prepared in the dept. of *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajyakalpna* at Ayurveda College.

6. Standardization of Drug

Standardization and authentication of drug material done from G.M.P. certified Company.

Route : Oral

Dose : 3 Gm (8 Hourly)

Anupan : *Jala*

Duration : 30 days

Follow up was taken on: Day 3, 5, 7, 9, 15, 21, 30.

Center of study: yashwant ayurvedic college, Kolhapur.

Type of study: Simple Randomized case study.

7. Discussion

Nidan Panchak

Hetu – stress, excess salt in diet, tea, tobacco chewing, *ratrijagrana*.

Purvarupa- *Avhykta*

Rupa- Anidra, Shirashoola, Bhrama, Daurbalya, Klama, Krodhaprachurya.

Upashay/anupashay—upashya with rest and medicine.

Differential Diagnosis- Essential hypertension, secondary hypertension.
Vyadhivinishyay- Essential hypertension.

SAMPRAPTI⁴

Table 1 : Showing Samprapti Ghataka

<i>Dosh</i>	<i>Vata, pitta.</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa, rakta.</i>
<i>Stotus</i>	<i>Rasavaha, raktavaha, manovaha.</i>

Discussion on DRUG:-5,6,7,8,9

Table 2 : Showing Action of Drugs on Disease

S r. N o	Content Latin Name	Guna	Rasa	Vipa k	Vee rya	Prab hav	Karma	Upayuktan g
1	Bilva-Aegle Marmelos	Laghu, Snigdha, Tikshna	KatuTikta Kashaya	Katu	Ush na		Shothahara (mutral)	Moola
2	Agnimanth- PremnaSerratifoli a	Laghu Ruksha	KatuTikta	Katu	Ush na			Moola
3	Gambhari- GmelinaArborea	Laghu ,Ruksha	Tikta,Kashaya,m adhura	Katu	Ush na		Shothahara, Hridya,Med hya	Moola
4	Patala- SterosprumSue olens	Laghu, Ruksha	Tikta,Kashaya	Katu	Ush na		Shothahara	Moola
5	Shyonak- OroxylumIndicum	Laghu, Ruksha	Tikta,Kashya,Kat u, Madhura	Katu	Ush na		Shothahara, Hrudya	Moola
6	Shaliparni- DesmodiumGang eticum	Guru, Snigdha	Madhura,Tikta	Madh ura	Sita		Shothahara	Moola
7	Prushniparni- UrariaPicta	Laghu, Sara	Madhura,Katu	Madh ura	Ush na			Moola
8	Bruhathi-Solanum Indicum	Laghu, Ruksha	Katu,Tikta	Katu	Ush na		Hrudhya	Moola,Phal a,Patra
9	Kanthakari- Solanum Virginianum	Laghu, Ruksha	Tikta,Katu	Katu	Ush na		Hrudhya	Panchang
10	Gokshuru- TribulusTerrestri s	Guru, Snigdha	Madhura	Madh ura	Sita		Mutral,Hr udhya	Moola,Phal a
11	Vacha (Acoruscalamus)	Laghu Tikshna	Katu, Tikta	Katu	Ush na	Med hya	Mutral, Medhya, Hrudya	Moola
12	Punarnava(Boera viadiffusa)	Laghu Ruksha	Kasha, Tikta	Katu	Ush na		MutralMedh ya	Panchang

1 3	<i>Ela(Elettariacard amomum)</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Madhura,katu</i>	<i>Madh ura</i>	<i>Shit a</i>		<i>MutralHrud ya</i>	<i>Panchang</i>
1 4	<i>Shankhapushpi (Convolvulus pluricaulis)</i>	<i>SnigdhaPi chhil</i>	<i>Kashay</i>	<i>Madh ur</i>	<i>Ush na</i>		<i>Medhya</i>	<i>Panchang</i>
1 5	<i>Jatamansi (Nordostachysjat amansi)</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Madur, KashayKatu</i>	<i>Madh ur</i>	<i>She et</i>		<i>Medhya</i>	<i>Moola</i>

8. Observation and Result

Table 3 : Showing Gradiation of Symptoms

Sr. No.	Lakshan	No (0)	Mild (1) Rarely. Relieves without medication	Moderate (2) Frequently. Relieves after sometime. Does not disturb daily activities.	Severe (3) Frequently. Severe. Disturbs daily activities. Requires medication.
1	Anidra			√	
2	Shirashoola			√	
3	Bhrama		√		
4	Daurbalya			√	
5	Klama		√		
6	Krodhaprachurya			√	

Table 4 : Showing Follow up According to Days

Sr. No.	Day of follow Up	3	5	7	9	15	23	30
	<i>Lakshana</i>							
1	<i>Anidra</i>	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
2	<i>Shirashool</i>	2	2	2	1	1	1	1
3	<i>Bhrama</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	<i>Daurbalya</i>	2	2	2	2	1	1	1
5	<i>Klama</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	<i>KrodhaPrachurya</i>	2	2	2	1	1	1	1
7	<i>Systolic BP</i>	158	150	150	150	140	140	140
8	<i>Distolic BP</i>	90	90	90	90	90	80	80

9. Conclusion

Ayurved has unique approach towards all disease. Since disease like hypertension has limitation in other pathy. Ayurved has best medicine without any side effect. This is single case study on

essential hypertension. Further, I will done many more cases to evaluate efficiency of *dahsmuladi churna* on essential hypertension.

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